

Strategies to Enhance Drivers Benefits and Establish an Intra-Corporate Social Business in Leading on-Demand Company (Ride Hailing)

Immanuel Bong

Master of Business Administration, Institut Teknologi Bandung

ABSTRACT: Driven by social mission and mandate of government towards Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), one of the leading Indonesia ride-hailing company (INDOJEK) has launched and run a drivers' welfare program named ProDrivers. The program is supposed to reducing drivers' expenses. In this research, author attempts to crack the dilemma, specifically the ProDrivers program, to not only creating social impact, but also generating a sustainable social business that can provide unlimited resource to sustain INDOJEK social initiative to drivers. Author has used mixed-method in deploying this research, both qualitative and quantitative. Data collection was conducted to both drivers (as ProDrivers beneficiaries) and internal ProDrivers team (as strategist and executor of ProDrivers program), through survey, interview and focus group discussion (FGD). Using theories, such as 9 core elements of marketing and marketing mix (7Ps) which provide insight on how to improve ProDrivers program adoption, and internal marketing to understand to which extent ProDrivers program has delivered to drivers. Aside of it, author also uses some tools, such as New Wave of Marketing to facilitate marketing improvement. Revenue Model to find alternatives which ProDrivers can earn income and also Social Business Model Canvas to discover new business model

KEYWORDS: Brand Awareness, Monetization, Marketing Improvement, Satisfaction, Sustainable Development Goals.

INTRODUCTION

INDOJEK is already part of a holding group, it is known as Indonesian Leading On-Demand Platform (Ride Hailing), and its holding group is one of the biggest tech ecosystem group in Indonesia. The balance between profitability and fair compensation for drivers become a complex issue and high-level business-threatening issue. INDOJEK as giant in ride-hailing industry constantly encounters many demanding inquiries from drivers. Aside of drivers inquiry, Indonesia government also has stipulated a rule in which applicators (ride-hailing service) should apply a 20% total charge fee which consists of 15% applicator commission and 5% extra fee that can be translated in various forms such as additional safety insurance, drivers extra facilities, additional operational helps for drivers.

In INDOJEK holding ESG framework in 2023, there are some SDGs target, such as poverty eradication (SDG 1), maintenance of health and well being of everyone within its ecosystem (SDG 3), enablement of social and economic transformation in the lives of stakeholders (SDG 8). These 3 SDGs are closely relevant when it comes to drivers condition. Drivers livelihood is central to the SDG agenda, and in particular INDOJEK mission. INDOJEK has a specific welfare program which is installed inside driver app. Driver app mainly consists of 4 menus, which are 'home', 'income', 'ProDrivers' and 'inbox'. ProDrivers is a program of which INDOJEK launched in 2016, that has consistently created impact in lives of more than 450.000 drivers every month and claimed to be able to help 15% of drivers operational cost on monthly basis (Latri, 2023). ProDrivers program has helped drivers in multi-categories, such as for vehicle maintenance, telecommunication package, insurance, scholarship, home credit, etc.

ProDrivers program is a co-funding program, meaning it depends not only on internal budget, but also from external funding to provide facilities to drivers. There is a huge challenge with regards to scalability of the program, which is caused by limited budget support, due to company's race towards profitability. INDOJEK can't afford to lose in profitability competition, because it may threaten its business survival. If the business is closed, then drivers will also be in huge problem of having no job and no income. However, on the other hand, INDOJEK is still obligated to support drivers livelihood in line with Decree of Transportation Ministry KP 667, in which INDOJEK charges drivers 5% fee for drivers extra facilities and also in line with its social impact mission and in fulfillment of ESG target & SDG goals.

Within 2024, in order to scale up ProDrivers program, INDOJEK aims to monetize drivers app through advertising business which will put under driver team scope of work. Having more than 2 million drivers in its ecosystem, drivers are huge captive market that can be additional revenue stream of INDOJEK. Aside of getting revenue, the profit will be allocated specifically to help ProDrivers

program to scale up to give bigger impact for drivers. This research will be conducted to assess drivers' current level of awareness & satisfaction towards ProDrivers program, to create business and marketing improvement in context of ProDrivers program in order to sustainably create more impact for drivers' livelihood, to successfully formulate executable monetization strategy that aims drivers as captive market and to operationalize the monetization strategy.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. *Nine Core Elements of Marketing*

Hermawan Kartajaya introduced "The Nine Core Elements of Marketing" (Fakhira, 2023) which is the core of marketing which consists of segmentation, targeting, positioning, differentiation, marketing mix, selling, brand, service, and process. We are also introduced STV-triangle which forms the foundation of all corporate operations, and is comprised of those nine marketing elements. The acronym representing strategy (mind-share), tactics (market-share), and value (heart-share), abbreviated as STV-triangle. Marketing strategy (Fakhira, 2023) is related with customer management. This involved an exploration phase which is part of the plan to comprehend market segmentation. A company needs to form a justification on the market environment. After that, the company can identify its target market to make efficient use of its resources. The last step is positioning, where the corporation has to plan offers that also affect the brand's reputation. Thus, the business can legitimately draw in new clients.

Tactics (Fakhira, 2024) include selling, marketing mix, and differentiation. A strategy that has been devised to engage potential clients is translated into specific procedures called tactics. The goal of differentiation is to stand out from the competition by combining the infrastructure, context, and content of what firm can offer to clients. Then, to give the business a competitive position in the market, the marketing mix consists of offer, access, and communication can be used with the 7Ps (promotion, place, pricing, product, process, physical evidence and people) as the most recommended model of marketing mix as per Manoj (2013) in Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies, replacing 4Ps: promotion, place, pricing, and product. In order to fulfill the vision and goal, the value component is used as brand management (Fakhira, 2023). This is done by creating a powerful brand that is bolstered by suitable service and efficient procedures. A brand is a resource that adds value for consumers by raising their level of satisfaction and helping them recognize product or service quality. Brand awareness and customer satisfaction will lead to loyalty. This fact is supported by Karunia (2021) that concluded in his research that brand loyalty among Honda Vario motorbike consumers in Samarinda city is significantly influenced by brand awareness and customer satisfaction. Brand awareness and customer satisfaction with the Honda Vario brand significantly influence brand loyalty towards Honda motorcycles.

More than simply logos and symbols, a brand's strength in the market relative to its rivals is measured by its brand equity. The components of brand equity are perceived quality, brand recognition, brand association, brand loyalty, and other brand assets (trademark, competitive advantage, and patents).

B. *New Wave Marketing*

Hermawan Kartajaya from book *New Wave Marketing* (2013) said that the nine core elements of marketing have been refined to create New Wave Marketing, which makes greater sense in the current time. The existence of New Wave Marketing does not imply the elimination of Legacy Marketing, which is suitable as a foundational framework; rather, it refers to altering the vertically oriented tactics to a more horizontal flow. The components of the nine core elements of marketing changes in this horizontal era. In other words, if we want to involve customers, the market is essentially a subject rather than an object because doing so would boost the development of marketing value. For instance, the change is from differentiation to codification, positioning to clarity, targeting to confirmation, and segmentation to communization. Co-creation, currency, communal activation, and conversation replace the four Ps of marketing mix (product, price, location, and promotion). Next, a brand turns into a character, a service into care, and a process into collaboration.

C. *Social Business Model Canvas*

Based on socialbusinessdesign.org, Alexander Osterwalder created the business model canvas (BMC) in 2008 as a one-page business model design website that illustrates the business model of an enterprise. However, BMC cannot be properly applied to institutions or businesses that place high priority on social missions in their products. Important aspects of nonprofit projects, especially those pertaining to their beneficiaries and their missions, were left out of the BMC. The Social Innovation Lab and Tandemic designs are the basis for Social Business Model Canvas (SBMC). It consists of thirteen basic elements, as you can see, this model explains in

detail how company generates, distributes, and retains value. Since organizations are built up of interrelated, entwined components, each block is firmly related to the others. There are 13 blocks in SBMC, which are Social Impact Mission, Beneficiaries, Core Intervention(s), Value for Beneficiaries, Customers, Value for Customers, Channels, Key Activities, Key Resources, Key Partners and Stakeholders, Cost Structure, Revenue Engines, and Surplus.

D. Revenue Model

In order for ProDrivers program to survive, INDOJEK should create a business model which can create revenue stream. Given the flexibility of ProDrivers program, where it has its own application page inside drivers application, there are numerous possibilities of revenue streams that can be made. Revenue will be transferred to ProDrivers budget pool which will be utilized to enhance drivers welfare. Based on landmarks.co, there are 17 Common Revenue Model, starting from Subscription, Subscription, Markup, Licensing, Advertising, Donation, Affiliate commission, Sponsors, Data Sales, Project-Based Services, Retainer-based services, Tickets, Events, Workshops, Royalties, Manufacture (D2C), Library Access, Rent/Lease, Community Access, and Marketplace.

E. Internal Marketing

According to Berry & Parasuraman as quoted by Kimura (2017), The goal of internal marketing is to draw in, nurture, inspire, and keep skilled workers by providing them with job-products that meet their needs. Internal marketing is the strategy of designing work products to meet human needs and the attitude of viewing employees as customers. Synthesizing definitions and phases of internal marketing, Ahmed & Hafiz (2013) defines 5 main elements of internal marketing, which are employee motivation and satisfaction, customer orientation and customer satisfaction, inter-functional coordination and integration, marketing-like approach, implementation of specific corporate or functional strategies. Drivers' satisfaction (as customer in this context theory) becomes an important metric which is assessed in this research, because it results in drivers' loyalty towards ProDrivers utilization. This is supported by research that has been done by Mulyono (2016), when students, acting as customers, are content because their expectations have been fulfilled, students will be motivated to pursue further studies at the same college due to their satisfaction. In addition, the students who express satisfaction would highly recommend their college to other potential students.

In this research, researcher may use elements above to assess how ProDrivers program can leverage INDOJEK drivers motivation towards being more customer-oriented, whether or not ProDrivers program help drivers to perform their task correctly, and whether or not ProDrivers program can extend company's service excellence to customers. In the internal team, researcher may also use internal marketing perspective to assess how inter-function the coordination of ProDrivers program, how the marketing approach is and whether or not ProDrivers program is utilized for specific corporate or functional strategies.

F. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

In order to understand current overall marketing performance, researcher will also deep dive 9 core elements of marketing, consisting of segmentation, targeting, positioning, selling, marketing mix (7Ps), differentiation, brand, service and process, then internal

marketing which explores about drivers motivation and satisfaction, drivers’ orientation towards customer satisfaction, inter-functional coordination and integration of ProDrivers program, marketing approach and implementation of specific corporate or functional strategies related to ProDrivers program. Finally, researcher will find out the possibility of implementing new wave marketing as part of marketing improvement. Monetization strategy will also be developed as part of making ProDrivers program sustainable in a long run. To ensure the strategy become comprehensive, researcher will utilize social business model canvas. Revenue model will help researcher to determine the most feasible revenue generator for ProDrivers program.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is begun with identifying problems that are existent revolving around ProDrivers program. After having concluded the problems, research objectives are made consisting of 4 points. In order to achieve the objectives in this research, researcher will conduct interview, survey and focus group discussion (FGD) which will be gathered from drivers and internal team ProDrivers. To garner complete data and informaton, primary data will be complemented with internal company data and literature review. All data and information gathered will be wielded to create marketing improvement, formulate monetization strategy and implementation plan. Then eventually, conclusions and recommendations will be targeted to answer all research questions and be based on the overall business improvement & strategy that have been made.

Figure 2. Research Flow

The research approach used for the study is descriptive research supported by both quantitative and qualitative methods, as well as exploratory research. Descriptive research is characterized by the preexisting development of precise research inquiries. Prior to initiating the research, the investigators (or researchers) possess a significant level of knowledge regarding the research problem. As a result, they are able to precisely determine what needs to be measured and establish suitable and particular methods for conducting the measurements (Smith & Albaum, 2005). According to Whitney (as cited in Nazir, 2005), descriptive research involves the exploration of facts with precise interpretation. Descriptive research aims to study issues within society, prevailing norms, specific situations, including relationships, activities, attitudes, perspectives, ongoing processes, and the influences of a particular phenomenon.

This research can also be categorized as exploratory, as it employs interviews to discover new patterns or ideas related to the marketing & business improvement of ProDrivers program. Therefore, this research address “what” and “how” to create a sustainable and scalable ProDrivers program for drivers. According to theory, exploratory research seeks to understand a phenomenon or event by probing into it (Gulo, 2002:18). As a result, exploratory research commonly uses qualitative research methods, particularly data collection through in-depth interviews.

A. Operational Definition of Variables

Table I. Operation Variables (Drivers)

To Drivers		
Theory	Construct	Operational Definition
Brand Association		how drivers might associate 'Swadaya' with something that help it stick in their minds, how related 'Swadaya' program with INDOJEK in drivers' mind
		how drivers are cognizant towards the program and everything related with the program, including the usage behavior, and comparison with similar program
Brand Awareness		how drivers are cognizant towards the program and everything related with the program, including the usage behavior, and comparison with similar program
		how drivers are cognizant towards the program and everything related with the program, including the usage behavior, and comparison with similar program
Internal Marketing	Employee motivation and satisfaction	how satisfied drivers towards the program and how it makes them more loyal and motivated as drivers
	Customer orientation and customer satisfaction	how motivated drivers to satisfy & prioritize customers because of the existence of Swadaya program
7Ps Marketing Mix	Product	quantity, quality and relevance of products and services provided by Swadaya with drivers needs
	Price	the perception of drivers towards the discount/ cashback and price consideration
	Place	easiness & suitability of redeem location
	Promotion	the mechanism, effectiveness, and attractiveness of information benefit given to drivers
	Process	quality and seamlessness of swadaya claim process
	Physical Evidence	the quality of user interface of Swadaya page and events
	People	the quality of service given by Gojek staff related with Swadaya program

Table II. Operation Variables (Internal Team)

To Internal Team ProDrivers HQ		
Theory	Construct	Operational Definition
9 Core Marketing	Segmentation	the way to identify potential market segments
	Targeting	the way to determine the prioritization of certain segment
	Positioning	the way ProDrivers wants to be remembered in drivers' mind that set it apart from other
	Differentiation	how ProDrivers internal team distinguish ProDrivers from other similar programs

	7Ps - Product:	ensuring consistency of ProDrivers products/ services performance and future development
	7Ps - Price:	strategy for ProDrivers team to determine pricing position of its benefits to remain competitive
	7Ps - Place:	channels/ medium to distribute ProDrivers benefits
	7Ps - Promotion:	way to ensure the benefit information given by ProDrivers can succeed and attract drivers to utilize ProDrivers products/ services
	7Ps - People:	overall performance, values and motivation of internal team of INDOJEK to ensure excellent delivery to drivers
	7Ps - Process:	entire steps that need to go through by drivers in order to receive ProDrivers program
	7Ps - Physical Evidence:	any tangible touch points that may convey ProDrivers benefits to drivers
	Selling	the process of delivering the benefits to drivers that may involve many touchpoints and stakeholders
	Brand	the way of internal ProDrivers team to build awareness, image, and salience of ProDrivers as a brand
	Service	ensuring service excellence of end-to-end ProDrivers to ascertain drivers' maximum satisfaction
	Process	internal management process of ProDrivers team to ensure maximum quality and efficiency for drivers
Internal Marketing	Inter-functional coordination and integration	coordination and integration of system outside ProDrivers inside the environment of INDOJEK to utilize/ assist ProDrivers program itself
	Marketing-like approach	general guideline in executing marketing/ getting traction from drivers
	Implementation of specific corporate or functional strategies	impact of ProDrivers program to internal corporate strategies/ tactics

B. Population & Samples

The population in this research consists of internal drivers team and drivers of INDOJEK. The number of the population of drivers INDOJEK is above 2 million. The subjects of this research are anyone within Greater Jakarta. For the quantitative approach, the sampling technique used is non-probability sampling, where every individual in the population does not have an equal chance of being sampled. The type of non-probability sampling to be used is convenience sampling. In convenience sampling, the researcher selects participants who are the easiest to reach/obtain (Gravetter & Forzano, 2012:151). The sample size for the quantitative approach in this research is 100 INDOJEK drivers. This follows the minimum sample size guidelines for descriptive research according to Fraenkel and Wallen (1993:92). The way researcher garner samples is by using internal company prominent placement, which is

banner inside ProDrivers menu, thus drivers that deign to fill in the questionnaire form can access it anytime. Survey is blasted and available to be filled from 5 to 11 April 2024 (for 1 week period).

The sampling technique for qualitative research in this study is typical case sampling. Typical case sampling is a method where a researcher tries to note specific criteria or characteristics related to cases that typically occur (Johnson & Christensen, 2014:270). This technique was chosen because the researcher aims to gain a perspective from specific drivers based on their perception towards ProDrivers program and from internal ProDrivers team regarding the implementation of ProDrivers program. Data collection for the qualitative approach is devided into 3 phases. Firslly, interview with ProDrivers internal team (exploratory), followed by FGD with drivers (exploratory, based on findings on observation and survey) and with ProDrivers internal team (result verification).

C. Data Analysis Technique

In this research, the researcher attempts to measure the ProDrivers program performance of marketing mix 7Ps using a Likert scale. A Likert scale is a tool used to measure a person's agreement or disagreement with a series of statements related to beliefs or behaviors about a specific object (Hermawan, 2009:132). The researcher uses a 5-point Likert scale.

To analyze qualitative data, researcher uses content analysis method. Content analysis is a widely used and widely recognized form of data analysis in research methodology. It can be utilized to analyze the data that has been documented in written form, images, and occasionally tangible items. The timing and application of this method will be contingent upon the research inquiries (Anusha, et al., 2023). Aside of it, the researcher also employs three steps according to Miles (as cited in Fachrudin, 2013:6).

1. Data Reduction involves summarizing and coding raw data, simplifying it, and creating clusters. Data reduction occurs continuously throughout the research.
2. Data Presentation aims to facilitate the researcher in drawing conclusions. Presentation methods include graphs, networks, charts, narrative text, and matrices.
3. Conclusions or verification are drawn continuously throughout the fieldwork. This process involves collecting data, identifying patterns, explanations, cause-and-effect relationships, and more.

In data analysis, the researcher employs triangulation. According to Paul Supomo (2008:71), triangulation is "viewing a reality from various perspectives, different aspects, to make it more credible and accurate. To conduct triangulation, we need to collect different types of data, use different data sources, collect data at different times, and even seek assistance from others to conduct research and record data."

RESULT & DISCUSSION

There are 676 valid responses which were received by researcher through online survey to INDOJEK drivers. Following theory used in this research, the minimum sample size guidelines for descriptive research according to Fraenkel and Wallen (1993:92) is only 100. Hence, this research is over-capable and delivered almost 7x from minimum sample required.

In order to test the validity of research instrument (Likert-scale questionnaires), based on theory, an indicator can be considered valid for a variable if the calculated r value is greater than the r table value. In this research, researcher uses the highest confidence level of 99%, with sample as big as 676 respondents, r table value is 0.097161 (following if sample is rounded-up to 700) and all research indicators are valid above r table value. All indicators are valid with significant correlation at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Based on theory used in this research, a variable is considered consistent if its reliability test value is greater than 0.60 (Nunnaly, as cited in Wijaya, 2011). Since the reliability score of all variables of this research is almost 1 (perfect), specifically at 0.977, thus indicators used in this research questionnaire are all reliable and accurate in measurement.

Based on survey conducted by researcher, overall mean score of brand awareness indicators is 4.27 (out of 5 scale), this means drivers use ProDrivers promo compared to other promo providers, have tendency to choose ProDrivers compared to other promo providers. However if research see specifically on 'BA19' indicator which assesses ProDrivers consideration before purchase, it only scored 4.07 comparatively lowest.

Table III. Brand Awareness Variable Overall Mean Score

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
BA15	676	4.41	1.104
BA16	676	4.29	1.195
BA19	676	4.07	1.265
Valid N (listwise)	676		

Based on theory used in this research, a variable is considered consistent if its reliability test value is greater than 0.60 (Nunnally, as cited in Wijaya, 2011). Since the reliability score of all variables of this research is almost 1 (perfect), specifically at 0.977, thus indicators used in this research questionnaire are all reliable and accurate in measurement.

Table IV. Internal Marketing Mean Score

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
IM21	676	4.02	1.226
IM22	676	4.17	1.134
IM23	676	4.17	1.152
IM24	676	4.26	1.128
IM25	676	4.28	1.105
IM26	676	4.26	1.106
IM27	676	4.23	1.133
Valid N (listwise)	676		

Regarding employees satisfaction and motivation (from indicator IM21 to IM25), the overall mean score is 4.18. From 5 indicators utilized here IM21 which talks about whether ProDrivers fulfills drivers' expectations is the lowest one. This may indicate that ProDrivers does help drivers, motivate drivers to work diligently, encourage drivers to be more loyal, ProDrivers still can do better than this to meet drivers' expectation.

Table V. Marketing Mix Mean Score

Descriptive Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
MM28	676	4.22	1.055
MM29	676	4.13	1.127
MM30	676	4.08	1.163
MM31	676	4.11	1.192
MM32	676	4.13	1.222
MM33	676	4.02	1.197
MM34	676	4.00	1.184
MM35	676	4.28	1.105
MM36	676	4.32	1.024
MM37	676	4.10	1.187
MM39	676	4.33	1.043
MM40	676	4.23	1.056
MM41	676	4.39	.964
MM42	676	4.13	1.139
MM44	243	4.59	.763
MM45	243	4.57	.792
Valid N (listwise)	243		

Firstly, researcher emphasize about product. Overall mean score of product variable (MM28 - MM30) is 4.14. Inside product variable, there are 3 indicators. The lowest point (MM30, with 4.08) talks about the fit between product & demand. This can be referred specifically to maintenance category, which was based on statement during FGD held by researcher, drivers mostly already have workshops that they usually go to or even do the service (simple ones) by themselves. For bike drivers, it's still plausible to go to chain-workshops that are already affiliated with ProDrivers, however for car drivers, it's not sensible since price gap between purchase in non-branded workshops and chain-workshops is quite far, it can be almost 30% (in this case, driver took car oil as example). Based on FGD, service category may be harder to penetrate drivers, because of existing formed behavior, trust issue and price consideration. Talking about price (MM31 - MM32) Price. Researcher asked about how helpful the amount of discount/ cashback (MM31) and how often drivers consider price before utilizing ProDrivers promo. The overall mean score of price variable is 4.12. Since MM31 score is 4.11, which means below variable score. This may indicate that the amount of discount/ cashback given to drivers can be better than this.

Place (MM33-MM35) variable is the third marketing mix variable. The overall mean score of this variable is 4.10. This variable talks about how easy to find affiliated outlets (MM33), how fit the brand/ merchant provided with drivers' needs (MM34) and claim or redemption easiness (MM35). In this context, easiness to find affiliated merchant got relatively lowest score (4.02) as well as fit between brands/ merchants with drivers' preference (4.00), while redemption easiness got much higher score at 4.28.

Promotion (MM36 - MM37) in this context talks about information effectiveness and attractiveness of ProDrivers advertisement. The overall mean score is 4.21. In terms of information, drivers already scored it higher (4.32), compared to attractiveness (4.10). This is pretty reasonable, knowing that ProDrivers advertisement is template-based. Aside of it, the banner used is repetitively used throughout the year of partnership. If there's no request by partner/ changes in detail, the advertisement will be the same. This may result in drivers become fatigue seeing the same advertisement, although the template that we use is very informative and made simple and easy-to-understand for drivers.

Process (MM39 - MM40) variable scores averagely at 4.28. This variable talks about overall purchasing process in ProDrivers and overall service quality of outlet staff (offline). These indicators score 4.33 and 4.23 respectively. These score are already quite good in comparison with several indicators above, showing that ProDrivers process or mechanism is easy to follow.

Physical Evidence variable (MM41 - MM42) talks about easy access/ navigation within ProDrivers menu and within ProDrivers offline event. Overall mean score of this variable is 4.26, while MM42 score (4.13) is lower quite significantly than MM41 (4.39). This means navigation within ProDrivers apps is already satisfying, however ProDrivers events are not as satisfying as its apps. Aside from ProDrivers event has more limited merchant offers due to limited space and also is conducted not so often, from FGD, there is also another point of view or answer to this reality.

There are only partial participants (35.8% of total respondents) that have interacted with INDOJEK staff in order to assess how helpful the staff in a sense of being informative whenever drivers want to know about ProDrivers (MM44) and how good the quality of staff in solving issue/ problems in regards to ProDrivers (MM45). The score is incredibly high, 4.59 and 4.57 respectively, with overall mean score 4.58. The result gathered from FGD aligns with the outcome of survey, drivers appreciate staff of INDOJEK (in all cases, including when they encountered difficulties related to ProDrivers program) because of staff hospitality.

This research has found consistent behavioral pattern despite age group, vehicle type and loyalty tier, most of drivers (54-67% of total respondents) open ProDrivers menu (the main access to utilize ProDrivers program) everyday. This aligns with FGD result which drivers admitted to always check on ProDrivers whenever they wait for order. There's a risk comes from gen Z age group since they might have behavior to check other promotions (aside of ProDrivers as promo source) as they are perceived as more tech savvy than millennial and gen X.

Aside of brand awareness concern, lower loyalty tier (Basic and Silver) also have lesser motivation & satisfaction compared to higher tier. This may be because ProDrivers program (some brands and products/ services) sometimes is targetted only to higher loyalty tier (Gold and Platinum). This is in line with marketing mix cross-tab, where price (promo level) and place (brands/ merchants availability) variables have lesser score from lower loyalty tier drivers (Basic and Silver).

In terms of brand recall, ProDrivers is already on top of drivers mind when it comes to 'saving program of INDOJEK'. The form of ProDrivers that drivers think is mostly in a form of vouchers, discount, phone credit (equivalent to internet data package). Having found 95% of respondents as ProDrivers users is a good sign of this research, which means drivers already experience ProDrivers

and can testify more accurately about ProDrivers. This research shows ProDrivers as a brand is chosen than any other promo options, although when it comes to pre-purchase consideration of ProDrivers, it scores lower than the prior.

Internet package is the most used program (more than 78% of respondents), followed by dailies and food purchases. This poses an opportunity for ProDrivers to get more dailies and meals partners, since the current range of partners of ProDrivers is with vehicle maintenance or automotive partners which is a mismatch between demand and supply (in fact only 5% of respondents have used vehicle service discount/ promo).

Drivers app as the most important ProDrivers touchpoint is the source where drivers know about ProDrivers. However event also helped drivers to know more about ProDrivers as well as friends. This shows Word-of-Mouth (WoM) strategy might also work to gain more brand awareness. Further, ProDrivers navigation bar is a main entry point to access ProDrivers, more than pop-up banner (although pop-up banner is more intrusive, because it appears everytime driver app is opened). Pop-up banner loading time and intrusive nature might hamper it to become an effective entry point of ProDrivers. This means ProDrivers menu promo banner (which is placed on top) should be optimized and become main focus of ProDrivers marketing (because as of now, pop-up banner has been more widely used as the prominent channel, more than promo banner). ProDrivers menu is also the point that may help drivers remember about ProDrivers (by 68% of respondents).

In terms of influence ProDrivers towards customer prioritization by drivers, this research found that ProDrivers has good impact on that, as well as, ProDrivers has quite satisfied drivers. However when it comes to meeting drivers' expectation, this indicator scores lower than any other inside internal marketing variable. The fit between demand and supply could be better. This aligns with the survey which shows only 5% of respondents have used vehicle service offers, in spite of 79% drivers already know that its available. In this part, drivers has shown researchers that there is a huge mismatch between expectation and ProDrivers direction.

There are 7 marketing mix, and researcher is intrigued to find which variable scores highest and lowest, as below.

VI. Marketing Mix Overall Mean Score Result

Marketing Mix	Score
Product	4.14
Price	4.12
Place	4.10
Promotion	4.21
Process	4.28
Physical Evidence	4.26
People	4.58

It's sensible that product, price and place scored lesser than other variables. Aside of mismatch of provided offers & demand (drivers may need more in dailies and meals category which currently are only few program/ partnership running, rather than vehicles promos), price becomes a concern for drivers, as they always need deeper rebate. Sometimes, drivers also found the price is quite confusing, that price of affiliated ProDrivers merchants products/ services are still higher due to being sold by branded merchants (this has correlation with place variables, where ProDrivers partners are branded merchants). This is a huge dilemma for ProDrivers team, because of limited resources, it's impossible to partner with local non-branded partners. Place also talks about outlet availability of which during FGD drivers informed about the concentration of ProDrivers affiliated merchants are mostly in city urban area, but less in rural area.

Marketing strategy that has been established by ProDrivers team is driven by certain criterias from internal (drivers) and external (partners). Segmentation by segregating drivers based on static criteria, such as type of vehicles and locations are the most common ones, since these criterias will determine the availability of programs (which are result of partnership with partners). ProDrivers program attempts to reach as much drivers as possible, ProDrivers always try to create impact as big as possible. However in certain programs, such as installment, ProDrivers needs to curate drivers based on income, loyalty level, tenure, etc. The common strategy to embrace new transating users, ProDrivers sometimes provides bigger benefit than usual to attract drivers to try using ProDrivers.

Positioning of ProDrivers is clear to provide benefit in a form of operational & also non-operational supports that are affordable and easy to access.

Talking about marketing tactics, ProDrivers has developed more features to differentiate it from any other promos provided by other platforms/ merchants, which is Daily Deduction Engine (DDE) which is utilized to deduct drivers' daily income and allocate the money to purchase discounted ProDrivers products/ services. This is very desirable for drivers, since drivers income is on daily basis. ProDrivers also expands their range of product category provided to drivers. As per FGD, drivers urge ProDrivers to provide small cash loan for all drivers, launch investment options, entertainment category, kids-specific needs, coffee places, and digital products (bills). Aside of expansion, ProDrivers is also suggested to improve current products/ services, such as longer-term internet package, original brand partners for vehicle maintenance, phone accessories, drugstore, more meals category, find more partners in dailies category, partner with Pertamina for fuel, improve installment and saving process, provide health, education and vehicle insurance. Aside of business part, ProDrivers also improves product especially ProDrivers menu to make ProDrivers program becomes more accessible for drivers, easy-to-discover promotion, and financial product development (which is able to show installment progress). ProDrivers also curates price or promotion that is proposed by partners to ensure it's more competitive than price/ promo in the market. Related to delivery of information about promotion, ProDrivers is improving banners (in terms of how it looks and refreshment to avoid ads fatigue), as well as push notification that can be triggered by ProDrivers team anytime needed (as of current push notification is handled by another communication team), voucher filter, and more intuitive POI maps (which can also show the promo valid in each store). ProDrivers also collaborates with Corporate Affairs (CA) to reserve online presence, as well as, utilizing drivers KOL to amplify ProDrivers impact and brand.

Open communication and trust among ProDrivers team member makes the team nimble and agile to progress developing ProDrivers program. Process that happened in internal ProDrivers is always begun from drivers' needs and desires, then the team will categorize it, tries to find source of products/ services (partners), creates best possible user journey and do prioritization. Improvement is usually done by conducting review throughout internal data or occasional research/ complaints gotten from drivers. Standard Operational Procedure (SOP) has been placed although it's heavily in operational process. For partners, there's no certain ProDrivers SOP established, except there's a specific program that requires it, for example KFC promo for drivers, we got special line for drivers (separated from customers) for easier flow for drivers.. Aside of it, partners use their regular operational standard procedures.

ProDrivers as an extension of INDOJEK is always deep-rooted in INDOJEK strive for excellence principle. To deliver best benefit for drivers, ProDrivers always uses multi-channels (online and offline), deliver new competitive products with proper promotional campaign. Service given to drivers should be flawless in navigation and level of affordability. Service and marketing strategy are supposed to be integrated in a sense whenever service given by ProDrivers/ affiliated ProDrivers partners are lacking, ProDrivers should revamp the product/ message/ journey itself. In practice, sometimes this is too good to be true, because of how complex the issue, but the resource to manage all of these are pretty limited.

ProDrivers works with multidivisions, at least 12 divisions, with communication team is the closest one, due to their role in filtering, scheduling and blasting information to drivers through pop-up banner and push notification. There are also lots of existing financial products from INDOJEK Financial. PDG (Product & Designer Group) team works hard to improve ProDrivers menu capability, as well as region team which is the extension of ProDrivers team in offline channels. ProDrivers is also included in government-related project, such as quarterly report to Transportation Ministry, as well as, sustainability roadmap of INDOJEK holdings to attain 3 net-zero by 2030 and to stabilize negative sentiments which occasionally occur through the implementation of new policy for drivers/ any social dynamics that may trigger it.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTION

Current level of awareness is high from INDOJEK drivers towards ProDrivers program. Based on brand recall with clue 'INDOJEK saving program for drivers', majority of respondents can mention 'ProDrivers' (65% of total respondents). When the clue was changed to 'operational support from INDOJEK', again 'ProDrivers' appeared on 2nd rank, after 'INDOJEK'. This fact is supported by the fact that more than 50% of total respondents open ProDrivers menu and heard/ encountered ProDrivers everyday. In terms of satisfaction towards ProDrivers, the result of survey shows that the overall score is quite good at 4.18 out of 5. Indicators in this variable indicate that ProDrivers does help drivers, motivate drivers to work diligently, encourage drivers to be more loyal, ProDrivers still can do better than this to meet drivers' expectation.

There are 12 business/ marketing improvements that ProDrivers can make as summarized below.

1. Provide new products/ services which are affordable and easy-to-access
2. All drivers should receive the best part (despite ProDrivers profit-oriented activities or benefit difference between loyalty tier levels)
3. Vehicle partners, dailies and meals options with affordable products and trusted products and services (low-tier brand with big chain networks).
4. Fast delivery of essential needs, by providing necessary needs through private label that can carry the depth of affordability, trust and customization as drivers need, like Bengkel ProDrivers.
5. Quarterly general survey of ProDrivers, to listen to drivers complaints and input/ feedback from drivers
6. Price watch, to flexibly follow market price trends in order to evaluate and adjust existing price and promo
7. Social Media into a community engagement, such as creating monthly competition that requires community involvement
8. Optimizing offline channels (such as kopdar which happens every month) as channel to converse about ProDrivers programs (inc. impression and complaints)
9. Referral program through drivers friends (as Word of Mouth is top #3 in terms of source of how drivers know about ProDrivers).
10. New agreement clauses which are incorporated into agreement to avoid any violation
11. Expand more categories, add more partners, refocus on what matters for drivers, not only on product categorial level, but also on SKU type-level. Broadening coverage to ensure more areas covered especially in rural areas.

There are also some executable monetization strategies that can utilize drivers as INDOJEK captive market. The revenue itself can be harvested either from drivers or partners. Start with monetization strategies that are most possible to do based on verification discussion with internal team, which are advertising model, affiliate commission model, project-based services and rent/ lease. However there are several models that are also possible though not specifically mentioned through FGD, which are licensing, donation, sponsorship. For further research of ProDrivers or any research that may cover topic in regards to captive market in business ecosystem. Researcher may suggest to also put emphasis on detail of each nature of categories provided, since each category has their own uniqueness and each market also has different perception and degree of acceptance depending on purchase power, preference, and etc. Aside of that, researcher also believes that doing deep analysis on customer journey to uncover pains and gains that customers feel will be beneficial to discover more specific issue and to gain more ideas in regards to platform development.

REFERENCES

1. Ahmed, Pervaiz. Hafiq, Mohammed. 2013. Internal Marketing. Taylor & Francis.
2. Anusha, Palagati. Kumar, Savuturu. Basha, Syed. 2023. Fundamentals of Research Methodology and Intellectual Property Rights. Redshine Publication.
3. Brown, D. M. Apostolidis, Chrysostomos. Singh, Pallavi. 2024. Sustainability starts from within: A critical analysis of internal marketing in supporting sustainable value co-creation in B2B organisations. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 117(Feb 2024), 14-27.
4. Fachrudin, Yudhi. 2013. Teknik Analisis Data Kualitatif. Makalah Metodologi Penelitian Universitas Syarif Hidayatullah, Jakarta.
5. Fakhira, Talitha. 2023. Mengupas 9 Elemen Pemasaran Menurut Hermawan Kartajaya. <https://contenthub.markplusinstitute.com/9-elemen-pemasaran-hk/#:~:text=Framework%20yang%20berisikan%20sembilan%20elemen,brand%2C%20service%2C%20dan%20process.>
6. Fakhira, Talitha. 2023. Menyusun Strategi Pemasaran Berdasarkan Konsep 9 Elemen Marketing. <https://contenthub.markplusinstitute.com/menyusun-strategi-pemasaran/>
7. Fakhira, Talitha. 2024. Melancarkan Strategi Dengan Taktik Pemasaran. <https://contenthub.markplusinstitute.com/taktik-pemasaran/>.
8. Fakhira, Talitha. 2024. Menciptakan Value Bagi Konsumen. <https://contenthub.markplusinstitute.com/menciptakan-value-bagi-konsumen/>
9. Fraenkel, J. R., & Wallen, N. E. 1993. How to Design and Evaluate Research in Education. Boston: McGraw Hill.

10. Gravetter, Frederick. Forzano, LoriAnn. 2012. Research Methods for the Behavioral Sciences, 4th edition. Belmont: Cengage Learning.
11. Gulo, W. 2002. Metodologi Penelitian. Jakarta: Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia
12. Hermawan, Asep. 2009. Penelitian Bisnis: Paradigma Kuantitatif. Jakarta: Grasindo.
13. Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., & Hoskisson, R. E. 2009. Strategic Management: Concepts and Cases: Competitiveness and Globalization. Mason: Cengage.
14. Johnson, Burke. Christensen, Larry. 2014. Educational Research 5th Edition: Quantitative, Qualitative, and Mixed Approaches. London: Sage Publication.
15. Kartajaya, Hermawan. 2013. New Wave Marketing. Jakarta: Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
16. Karunia, E. (2021). Brand Awareness dan Brand Experience terhadap Brand Satisfaction, Brand Trust dan Brand Loyalty. FORUM EKONOMI, 23(3), 606-624.
17. Kimura, T. 2017. Internal Marketing: Another Approach to Marketing for Growth. Taylor & Francis.
18. Landmarklabs. <https://www.landmarklabs.co/block/revenue-model-types>
19. Lastri, Made. 2023. PT XYZ Klaim Program ProDrivers Ringankan Biaya Operasional Driver. [https://www.detik.com/bali/bisnis/d-6736918/PT XYZ-klaim-program-ProDrivers-ringankan-biaya-operasional-driver](https://www.detik.com/bali/bisnis/d-6736918/PT-XYZ-klaim-program-ProDrivers-ringankan-biaya-operasional-driver).
20. Manoj, K. 2013. An Analysis of Marketing Mix: 7Ps or More (1st ed., Vol. 4). Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies.
21. Michaux, Stephanie. 2015. Porter's Five Forces: Stay Ahead of Competition. 50Minutes.com.
22. Mulyono, H. (2016). BRAND AWARENESS AND BRAND IMAGE OF DECISION MAKING ON UNIVERSITY. JMK: Jurnal Manajemen dan Kewirausahaan, 18(2), 163-173. 10.9744/jmk.18.2.163-173
23. Nazir, Moh. 2005. Metode penelitian. Bogor: Ghalia Indonesia.
24. PT XYZ. 2023. Group Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Framework. chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://assets.tokopedia.net/asts/PTXYZGroup_Group%20ESG%20Framework%202023.pdf
25. Santoso, Singgih. 2009. Panduan Lengkap Menguasai Statistik dengan SPSS 17. Jakarta: PT Elex Media Komputindo.
26. Smith, S. M., & Albaum, G. S. 2005. Fundamentals of Marketing Research. SAGE Publications.
27. Social Business Design. <https://socialbusinessdesign.org/what-is-a-social-business-model-canvas/>
28. Supomo, P. 2008. Manajemen Organisasi. Jakarta: CV Pustaka Setia.

Cite this Article: Imanuel Bong (2024). Strategies to Enhance Drivers Benefits and Establish an Intra-Corporate Social Business in Leading on-Demand Company (Ride Hailing). International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(7), 5555-5567